

Wireless Jamming Networks

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ABSTRACT

A mobile jammer is a device which is used to jam signals of a cell phone from receiving signals from base stations. Mobile jammer is used majorly where the disturbances that are occurred with the cell phones. So, in this paper we are designing a new Mobile Jammer unit which is capable of blocking the working of a cell phone from not receiving signal from Base Station. This was implemented using FPGA by interfacing Mobile Device, RF Transmitter and RF Receiver and LCD Unit. Keywords— Jammers, Mobile Jammer, FPGA, RF Transmitter, RF Receiver, LCD

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INTRODUCTION

Cell phones are everywhere these days. According to the Cellular Telecommunications and Internet Association, almost 195 million people in the United States had cell-phone service in October 2005. And cell phones are even more ubiquitous in Europe. The mobile phone or mobile, also called a wireless, cellular phone, cell phone, cell or hand phone (HP), is a long-range, portable electronic device used for mobile communication that uses a network of specialized base stations known as cell sites. In addition to the standard voice function of a telephone, current mobile phones may support many additional services, and accessories, such as SMS for text messaging, email, packet switching for access to the Internet, and MMS for sending and receiving photos and video. Most current mobile phones connect to a cellular network of base stations (cell sites), which is in turn interconnected to the public switched telephone network (PSTN) (the exception is satellite phones). Cell phones are basically handheld two-way radios. And like any radio, the signal can be disrupted, or jammed.

I. INSIDE A DIGITAL CELL PHONE

If you take a basic digital cell phone apart, you find that circuit board that contains

- A keyboard
- A liquid crystal display (LCD)
- An antenna
- The phone and A battery
- A speaker
- A microphone
- Remote control

II. JAMMING BASICS

Disrupting a cell phone is the same as jamming any other type of radio communication. A cell phone works by communicating with its service network through a cell tower or base station. Cell towers divide a city into small areas, or cells. As a cell-phone user drives down the street, the signal is handed from tower to tower. A jamming device transmits on the same radio frequencies as the cell phone, disrupting the communication between the phone and the cell-phone base station in the tower. Cell Phone Jammer is an instrument that prevent cellular phone from receiving and transmitting the mobile signals to the base station. Mobile Cell Phone Jammer can block all kinds of mobile phone's ringing sound at all places such as church, mosque, library, Movie Theater and meeting room. You just buy it and just attach it at some place. And you will never hear the bell sound of mobile phone any more.

Fig1. A Mobile Jammer

III. NEED OF JAMMERS

The rapid proliferation of cell phones at the beginning of the 21st century to near ubiquitous status eventually raised problems, such as their potential use to invade privacy or contribute to academic cheating. In addition, public backlash was growing against the disruption cell phones introduced in daily life. While older analog cell phones often suffered from poor reception and could even be disconnected by simple interference such as high frequency noise, increasingly sophisticated digital phones have led to more elaborate counters. Cell phone jamming devices are an alternative to more expensive measures against cell phones, such as Faraday cages, which are mostly suitable as built in protection for structures. They were originally developed for law enforcement and the military to interrupt communications by criminals and terrorists. Some were also designed to foil the use of certain remotely detonated explosives. The civilian applications were apparent, so over time many companies originally contracted to design jammers for government use switched over to sell these devices to private entities. Since then, there has been a slow but steady increase in their purchase and use, especially in major metropolitan areas. As with other radio jamming, cell phone jammers block cell phone use by sending out radio waves along the same frequencies that cellular phones use. This causes enough interference with the communication between cell phones and towers to render the phones unusable. On most retail phones, the network would simply appear out of range. Most cell phones use different bands to send and receive communications from towers (called frequency division duplexing, FDD). Jammers can work by either disrupting phone to tower frequencies or tower to phone frequencies. Smaller handheld models block all bands from 800 MHz to 1900 MHz within a 30-foot range (9 meters). Small devices tend to use the former method, while larger more expensive models may interfere directly with the tower. The radius of cell phone jammers can range from a dozen feet for pocket models to kilometers for more dedicated units. The TRJ-89 jammer can block cellular communications for a 5-mile (8 km) radius. Less energy is required to disrupt signal from tower to mobile phone than the signal from mobile phone to the tower (also called base station), because the base station is located at larger distance from the jammer than the mobile phone and that is why the signal from the tower is not as strong. Older jammers sometimes were limited to working on phones using only analog or older digital mobile phone standards. Newer

models such as the double and triple band jammers can block all widely used systems (CDMA, iDEN, GSM, et al.) and are even very effective against newer phones which hop to different frequencies and systems when interfered with. As the dominant network technology and frequencies used for mobile phones vary worldwide, some work only in specific regions such as Europe or North America. Some Cell Phone Jammers have been introduced to some State Prisons in the United States. Cell phones that have been sneaked into prison pose a security risk for guards and property owners living nearby.

IV. PROBLEMS IN EXISTING JAMMERS

Envisage a situation where you are essaying to dial 911 and cannot get through because someone has a cell phone jammer with him. Otherwise, you want to call the police to avoid a robbery in your building but the robber has a cell phone jammer with him. So, what could you do in such a dangerous situation? Jamming devices utilized with some thoughts may be much more useful than just a method of enjoyment. To remove these hazards a new efficient type of mobile jammer is proposed using FPGA. In this new design we are going to disable the keypad, MIC, speaker, will be only disabled by using the FPGA & we doing it using a 400MHz frequency which has an public license so there is no need of licensing. The person didn't even get the notification .Some of the Common Problems are listed below: call or message when he is in the jammer coverage The person cannot be contacted . Nearly the mobile phone will be in Switch Off mode. There will not be any notification that the user mobile has been jammed.

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM DESIGN

In most countries, it is illegal for private citizens to jam cell-phone transmission, but some countries are allowing businesses and government organizations to install jammers in areas where cell-phone use is seen as a public nuisance. In December 2004, France legalized cell-phone jammers in movie theaters, concert halls and other places with performances. France is finalizing technology that will let calls to emergency services go through. India has installed jammers in parliament and some prisons. It has been reported that universities in Italy have adopted the technology to prevent cheating. Students were taking photos of tests with their camera phones and sending them to classmates.

VI. ALTERNATIVES TO CELL PHONE

JAMMING While the law clearly prohibits using a device to actively disrupt a cell-phone signal, there are no rules against passive cell-phone blocking. That means using things like wallpaper or building materials embedded with metal fragments to prevent cell-phone signals from reaching inside or outside the room. Some buildings have designs that block radio signals by accident due to thick concrete walls or a steel skeleton. Companies are working on devices that control a cell phone but do not "jam the signal." One device sends incoming calls to voicemail and blocks outgoing calls. The argument is that the phone still works, so it is technically not being jammed. It is a legal gray area that has not been ruled on by the FCC as of April 2005. Cell-phone alters are available that indicate the presence of a cell-phone signal. These have been used in hospitals where cell-phone signals could interfere with sensitive medical equipment. When a signal is detected, users are asked to turn off their phones. For a less technical solution, Caudal Partners, a design firm in Chicago, has launched the SHHH, the Society for Handheld Hushing. At its Web site, you can download a note to hand to people conducting annoying cell-phone conversations, expressing your lack of interest in what they're talking about.

Fig.2. General Block Diagram of Mobile Jammer

VII. FIELD PROGRAMABLE GATE ARRAY

A Field-programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is an integrated circuit designed to be configured by the customer or designer after manufacturing—hence "field-programmable". The FPGA configuration is generally specified using a hardware description language (HDL), similar to that used for an application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) (circuit diagrams were previously used to specify the configuration, as they were for ASICs, but this is increasingly rare). FPGAs can be used to implement any logical function that an ASIC could perform. The ability to update the functionality after shipping,

partial re-configuration of the portion of the design[1] and the low non-recurring engineering costs relative to an ASIC design (notwithstanding the generally higher unit cost), offer advantages for many applications. In addition to digital functions, some FPGAs have analog features. The most common analog feature is programmable slew rate and drive strength on each output pin, allowing the engineer to set slow rates on lightly loaded pins that would otherwise ring unacceptably, and to set stronger, faster rates on heavily loaded pins on high-speed channels that would otherwise run too slow. Another relatively common analog feature is differential comparators on input pins designed to be connected to differential signaling channels. A few "mixed signal FPGAs" have integrated peripheral Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs) and Digital-to-Analog Converters (DACs) with analog signal conditioning blocks allowing them to operate as a system-on-a-chip. Such devices blur the line between an FPGA, which carries digital ones and zeros on its internal programmable interconnect fabric, and field-programmable analog array (FPAA), which carries analog values on its internal programmable interconnect fabric. FPGAs contain programmable logic components called "logic blocks", and a hierarchy of reconfigurable interconnects that allow the blocks to be "wired together"—somewhat like many (changeable) logic gates that can be inter-wired in (many) different configurations. Logic blocks can be configured to perform complex combinational functions, or merely simple logic gates like AND and XOR. In most FPGAs, the logic blocks also include memory elements, which may be simple flip-flops or more complete blocks of memory.

VII. RF ENCODER AND DECODER

A.General Encoder and Decoder Operations

The Holtek HT-12E IC encodes 12-bits of information and serially transmits this data on receipt of a Transmit Enable, or a LOW signal on pin-14 /TE. Pin-17 the D_OUT pin of the HT-12E serially transmits whatever data is available on pins 10,11,12 and 13, or D0,D1,D2 and D3. Data is transmitted at a frequency selected by the external oscillator resistor. By using the switches attached to the data pins on the HT-12E, as shown in the schematic, we can select the information in binary format to send to the receiver. The receiver section consists of the Ming RE-99 and the HT-12D decoder IC. The DATA_IN pin-14 of the HT-12D reads the 12-bit binary information sent by the HT-12E and then places this data on its output pins. Pins 10,11,12 and 13 are the data out pins of the

HT-12D, D0,D1,D2 and D3. The HT-12D receives the 12-bit word and interprets the first 8-bits as address and the last 4-bits as data. Pins 1-8 of the HT-12E are the address pins. Using the address pins of the HT-12E, we can select different addresses for up to 256 receivers. The address is determined by setting pins 1-8 on the HT-12E to ground, or just leaving them open. The address selected on the HT-12E circuit must match the address selected on the HT-12D circuit (exactly), or the information will be ignored by the receiving circuit.

When the received addresses from the encoder matches the decoders, the Valid Transmission pin-17 of the HT-12D will go HIGH to indicate that a valid transmission has been received and the 4-bits of data are latched to the data output pins, 10-13. The transistor circuit shown in the schematic will use the VT, or valid transmission pin to light the LED. When the VT pin goes HIGH it turns on the 2N2222 transistor which in turn delivers power to the LED providing a visual indication of a valid transmission reception. B. Controlling the Project with a FPGA Using these RF transmitter & receiver circuits with a FPGA would be simple. We can simply replace the switches used for selecting data on the HT-12E with the output pins of the FPGA. Also we can use another output pin to select TE, or transmit enable on the HT-12E. By taking pin-14 LOW we cause the transmitter section to transmit the data on pins 10-13. To receive information simply hook up the HT-12D output pins to the FPGA. The VT, or valid transmission pin of the HT-12D could signal the FPGA to grab the 4-bits of data from the data output pins. If you are using a FPGA with interrupt capabilities, use the VT pin to cause a jump to an interrupt vector and process the received data. The HT-12D data output pins will LATCH and remain in this state until another valid transmission is received. NOTE: You will notice that in both schematics each of the Holtek chips have resistors attached to pins 15 and 16. These resistors must be the exact values shown in the schematic. These resistors set the internal oscillators of the HT-12E/HT-12D. It is recommended that you choose a 1% resistor for each of these resistors to ensure the correct circuit oscillation. C. Range of Operation The normal operating range using (only) the LOOP TRACE ANTENNA on the transmitter board is about 50 feet. By connecting a quarter wave antenna using 9.36 inches of 22 gauge wire to both circuits, you can extend this range to several hundred feet. Your actual range may vary due to your finished circuit design

and environmental conditions. The transistors and diodes can be substituted with any common equivalent type. These will normally depend on the types and capacities of the particular loads you want to control and should be selected accordingly for your intended application.

VIII. RF DETAILS

The TWS-434 and RWS-434 are extremely small, and are excellent for applications requiring short-range RF remote controls. The transmitter module is only 1/3 the size of a standard postage stamp, and can easily be placed inside a small plastic enclosure. TWS-434: The transmitter output is up to 8mW at 433.92MHz with a range of approximately 400 foot (open area) outdoors. Indoors, the range is approximately 200 foot, and will go through most walls.

TWS-434 transmitter accepts both linear and digital inputs, can operate from 1.5 to 12 Volts-DC, and makes building a miniature hand-held RF transmitter very easy. The TWS-434 is approximately the size of a standard postage stamp.

TWS-434RF Receiver operates at 433.92MHz Frequency and at Voltage: 4.5V~5.5V and Bit-rate: 0.2kbps-4kbps

IX. LCD DISPLAY

Reading data from the LCD is done in the same way, but control line R/W has to be high. When we send a high to the LCD, it will reset and wait for instructions. Typical instructions sent to LCD display after a reset are: turning on a display, turning on a cursor and writing characters from left to right. When the LCD is initialized, it is ready to continue receiving data or instructions. If it receives a character, it will write it on the display and move the cursor one space to the right. The Cursor marks the next location where a character will be written. When we want to write a string of characters, first we need to set up the starting address, and then send one character at a time. Characters that can be shown on the display are stored in data display (DD) RAM. The size of DDRAM is 80 bytes. More FPGA devices are using 'smart LCD' displays to output visual information. The following discussion covers the connection of a 16x2 LCD display to a PIC FPGA. LCD displays designed around Hitachi's LCD HD44780 module, are inexpensive, easy to use, and it is even possible to produce a readout using the 8 x 80 pixels of the display. Hitachi LCD displays have a standard ASCII set of characters plus Japanese, Greek and

mathematical symbols. For a 8-bit data bus, the display requires a +5V supply plus 11 I/O lines. For a 4-bit data bus it only requires the supply lines plus seven extra lines. When the LCD display is not enabled, data lines are tri-state which means they are in a state of high impedance (as though they are disconnected) and this means they do not interfere with the operation of the FPGA when the display is not being addressed.

Fig 3: Pictures of our Proposed Mobile jammer

X. CONCLUSIONS

Our projected Mobile jammer is functioning utterly while not moving the signals from the network. In order that the user will be able to get the notifications relating to Calls and messages (SMS, MMS). The notifications regarding the calls are given to the user. If there's any imperative decision as we will get the notification we will leave from the coverage space and use our mobile because it is. No would like of licensing. Implementation of our freshly designed jammers is straightforward. As we tend to square measure employing a FPGA, our hardware will be changed whenever we would like. Will be enforced wherever silence to be maintained. Future modifications square measure attainable simply. Misuse of mobiles will be restricted. So our Mobile jammers will offer higher potency with lower misuses.

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